

Strain name	genotype	construct	source
CEN.PK2-1C83	MATa MAL2-8c SUC2	<i>Mig1-GFP-KanMx</i> <i>Nrd1-mCherry-hphNT1</i>	K.D. Entian, Frankfurt am Main, Germany, Fluorescence tag: this study
KOY.HXT1P	KOY.VW100 integration into cassette: <i>HXT7 prom-HXT1-HXT7 term</i> <i>ura3-52::URA3</i>	<i>Mig1-GFP-KanMx</i> <i>Nrd1-mCherry-hphNT1</i>	[1], fluorescence tag: this study
KOY.HXT7P	KOY.VW100 integration into cassette: <i>HXT7 prom-HXT7-HXT7 term</i> <i>ura3-52::URA3</i>	<i>Mig1-GFP-KanMx</i> <i>Nrd1-mCherry-hphNT1</i>	[1], fluorescence tag: this study
KOY.TM6*P	KOY.VW100 integration into cassette: <i>HXT7 prom-TM6*-HXT7 term</i> <i>ura3-52::URA3</i>	<i>Mig1-GFP-KanMx</i> <i>Nrd1-mCherry-hphNT1</i>	[1], fluorescence tag: this study
HXT7-GFP	MATa MAL2-8c SUC2 HXT7-GFP::Hix3MX6	<i>Mig1-GFP-KanMx</i> <i>Nrd1-mCherry-hphNT1</i>	[2], transfer of construct to new background: this study

Table S2. *S. cerevisiae* strains used in this study